

Development And Validation of Colorimetric Method for Quercetin in Capsules

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ABSTRACT

Quercetin, a potent anti-inflammatory drug a potent flavonoid found in fruits, vegetables, leaves, seeds & grains, it works by inhibiting cytochrome P450, CYP3A4, CYP2C19 enzyme, reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines, scavenge free radical and stabilize mast cell, which helps to mitigate chronic disease and promote the overall health. A simple, rapid precise and reproducible colorimetric method has been developed and validated for determination for Quercetin in formulation (capsules). Quercetin showed maximum absorbance at 371nm in solvent, methanol. All validation parameters such as linearity, range, LOD, LOQ and precision were evaluated as per ICH guidelines Q2 (R2). Linearity was observed in the concentration range of 0.1-50 ug/ml and its mean correlation coefficient was 0.999. The LOD and LOQ for Quercetin was found to be 0.022683 and 0.068735 µg/ml respectively. The percentage mean recovery at three different levels (80%, 100%, and 120%) ranged between 99.83% to 103%w/w & the percentage assay of Quercetin in capsules was found to be 99.65-99.88 %w/w. The developed colorimetric method was found to be specific, accurate, precise, linear and can be successfully applied for routine analysis of Quercetin in formulation (capsules).

Keywords: Colorimetric Method, ICH guidelines, Quercetin

INTRODUCTION

Quercetin is a novel anti-inflammatory agent used in the treatment of allergies and asthma^{1,2}. It works by multiple mechanisms of action and has been shown to inhibits inflammatory enzyme (cox-2), reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF α), scavengers free radicals and stabilizes mast cell. It is regulated by the FDA as a dietary supplement under the Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act (DSHEA) and DCGI approved as a dietary supplement in India^{3,4}. Few methods have been reported in literature for determination of Quercetin⁵⁻⁸ and this work, describes the development and validation of a Colorimetric method for estimation of Quercetin in capsules.

Fig 1: Structure of Quercetin EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY: -

Instruments:

Electronic weighing balance (Sartorius TE214S)&UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1900i).The Chemicals and Reagents used were Methanol (HPLC grade), standard Quercetin, and Quercetin Capsules.

METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of standard stock solution and working standard solution:

Accurately weighed 10mg of Quercetin standard and transferred into 10ml volumetric flask, 3- 5ml of methanol was added and sonicated for 3min to dissolve it completely, volume was made up with methanol to 10 ml to get 1000µg/ml of standard Quercetin solution and labeled as STD Stock Quercetin and labelled as Standard stock solution.

Further 1 ml was diluted to 10 ml to get 100 µg/ml solution of **Working Standard Solution I**. Further

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0.1 ml was diluted to 10 ml to get 10 µg/ml labelled as **Working Standard Solution II**.

Preparation of Quercetin sample solution

From the standard stock solution, the following volume of solution was pipetted out in 6 different 10ml volumetric flasks and to each solution 10ml of methanol was added.

Working standard solution II of Quercetin (10µg/ml) in methanol was scanned in UV-visible region of 200-800nm using 1900i-Shimadzu-UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The visible spectrum was observed and the optimum wavelength at which Quercetin shows good absorbance was selected and the spectrum obtained is presented in **Fig2**.

VALIDATION OF COLORIMETRIC METHOD FOR QUERCETIN

Colorimetric method for determination of Quercetin was validated as per ICH guidelines Q2(R2)⁹ for linearity and range LOD, LOQ, Accuracy, precision and robustness.

LINEARITY AND RANGE:

The linearity of an analytical procedure specifies the results which are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample, The linearity was determined by analyzing absorbance of the Quercetin of concentration (0.1µg/ml - 50µg/ml) at 371nm against 10ml methanol as blank. The calibration curve was plotted using concentration against absorbance. A regression equation and Correlation Coefficient were determined for Quercetin standard concentrations.

Calibration curve for Quercetin

From **working standard solution II**, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask, volume was made up to 10 ml with methanol to get concentration of 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 µg/ml solution of Quercetin.

From the **working standard solution I** 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2 & 5 ml aliquot were pipetted out separately in a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up with the methanol solvent to

obtain the concentrations of 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50 µg/ml solution of Quercetin.

The absorbance of all the solutions was measured at 371nm. The calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance VS concentration of the drug and regression equation was computed. The data and standard calibration curve obtained is presented in **Fig.3 & Table 1**.

Linear Regression analysis data obtained for calibration curve of Quercetin is presented in **Table.2**.

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD)

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. The LOD was estimated from the set of five calibration curves values used to determine method linearity. LOD was calculated as:

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3.3 \times \text{Standard deviation of Y-Intercept } (\sigma)}{\text{Average slope of 6 calibration curves}}$$

Where (σ), Standard deviation of the Y- Intercept of the 6 calibration curve values. S- Mean slope of the five calibration curve values.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION(LOQ)

The Quantitation limit is a parameter of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample which can be quantified, The LOQ was estimated from the set of five calibration curves used to determine method linearity, LOQ was calculated as

$$\text{LOQ} = \frac{10 \times \text{Standard deviation of Y-Intercept } (\sigma)}{\text{Average slope of 6 calibration curves}}$$

Where (σ), Standard deviation of the Y- Intercept of the 6 calibration curve values. S- Mean slope of the five calibration curve values.

Both LOD and LOQ values are presented in **Table.3**.

ACCURACY:

The Accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found, the obtained values are presented in **Table4 & Fig 4**.

Acceptance Criteria: Percentage recovery should be 95-105%w/w.

PRECISION:

The precision of the method was determined by Intraday, inter-day, repeatability and reproducibility studies.

INTRADAY AND INTERDAY:

The inter-day and Intraday studies were determined by measuring the absorbance at different time intervals (morning, afternoon and evening) on the same day (Inter day and on three consecutive days (Intraday precision) for solution of Quercetin The mean of absorbance, SD and % RSD was calculated. The data obtained for intra and inter day studies have been tabulated and represented in **Table5**.

REPEATABILITY:

For repeatability studies, 10µg/ml of standard stock solution was transferred into 10ml volumetric flask and volume was made-up to the mark with solvent system of 10ml methanol and analyzed six times on the same day at the same time. The absorbance was recorded, mean, SD, and %RSD was calculated. The results obtained for Repeatability studies have been tabulated & represented in **Table6 & Fig 5**.

Sandell's sensitivity

The sensitivity depends upon the experimental conditions. The maximum sensitivity of which a method is capable is expressed in terms of detection limits. Knowledge of sensitivity must be obtained by small changes in the concentration. In this manner very small amounts of the constituents can be determined.

The Sandell's sensitivity, molar absorptivity, standard deviation, coefficient of variance, slope and intercept, for all the methods will be calculated through the following formulation.

Formula to calculate Sandell's Sensitivity:

$$\text{Sandell's sensitivity} = \frac{\text{concentration of drug} \times 0.001}{\text{Absorbance}}$$

METHODOLOGY FOR DETERMINATION OF QUERCETIN IN CAPSULE FORMULATION

Capsule Name: QUERCETIN Label claim: 100mg of Quercetin

Brand company: DECODE AGE

Procedure: 1ml of sample stock solution was taken in 3 different 10ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with methanol solvent to the mark. The absorbance was recorded and the % assay & % RSD for assay was calculated.

$$\% \text{ ASSAY} = \frac{\text{absorbance of sample} \times \text{concentration} \times \text{DF} \times 100}{\text{absorbance of standard} \times \text{weight of sample} \times \text{label claim}}$$

The data obtained for %Assay and %RSD for assay of Quercetin has been tabulated in **Table 7**.

RESULTS FOR DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF COLORIMETRIC METHOD

Colorimetric method was developed for estimation of Quercetin in bulk and in formulation, the results obtained are presented below.

Standard solution of Quercetin containing 10 µg/ml was scanned in the spectrum mode from 200nm to 800 nm with methanol & the spectra obtained is presented.

Fig 2: UV spectra for Quercetin(10µg/ml) in methanol

LINEARITY AND RANGE:**Table 1: Linearity data for Quercetin**

Sl.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance*
1	0	0
2	0.1	0.013
3	0.2	0.02
4	0.5	0.0531
5	1	0.0931
6	2	0.17
7	5	0.433
8	10	0.866
9	20	1.732
10	50	4.00

*Average of 3 readings

Fig 3: Calibration graph for linearity and range for Quercetin**Table 2: Linear regression analysis data for Quercetin**

PARAMETERS	QUERCETIN
Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.1-50
Linearity range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.1-50
Correlation coefficient(R^2)	0.999
Slope	0.0805
Intercept	0.0234

Table 3: Results for LOD and LOQ studies for Quercetin

PARAMETER	QUERCETIN
Mean of y- intercept	0.0234
SD of slope	0.0805
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.022683
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.068735

LIMIT OF DETECTION AND LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION:**ACCURACY:**

Accuracy studies was performed at 3 different levels (80%, 100%, 120%) and %recovery of Quercetin was calculated and presented below,

Table 4: % Recovery data of Quercetin for accuracy studies at 3 different levels

Conc. of standard (µg/ml) A	Conc. of sample (µg/ml) B	Total conc. (A+B) (µg/ml)	Abs* for mixtures (A+B)	Conc. of standard (µg/ml)	Recovery of standard (µg/ml)	%Recovery of std(w/w)
8	10	18	1.600	18.25	8.24	103
10	10	20	1.762	20.09	10.09	100.9
12	10	22	1.928	21.98	11.98	99.83

*Average of 3 readings

Fig 4: Overlaid spectrum for accuracy studies of at three different levels**PRECISION****INTERDAY AND INTRADAY****Table 5: Data for Inter-day and Intra-day studies for Quercetin.**

INTER-DAY		INTRA-DAY	
TIME (Hrs)	Mean absorbance*(n=3) Quercetin(µg/ml)	TIME (Day)	Mean absorbance*(n=3) Quercetin(µg/ml)
0	0.880	1	0.871
2	0.869	2	0.853
4	0.867	3	0.845
Mean	0.871333	Mean	0.856333
SD	0.007	SD	0.013317
%RSD	0.802752	%RSD	1.555079

*Average of 3 readings

results with same solution on the same day and same time.

REPEATABILITY

The test for repeatability was performed to check whether the developed method gives consistent

Table 6: Data for Repeatability studies of Quercetin

SL.NO.	CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	ABSORBANCE
1	0.1	0.879
2	0.1	0.878
3	0.1	0.876
4	0.1	0.885

5	0.1	0.880
6	0.1	0.884
7	MEAN	0.880333
8	SD	0.003502
9	%RSD	0.397847

*Average of 6 readings

Fig 5: Overlaid spectrum for repeatability studies for Quercetin

Sandell's sensitivity: -

$$\text{Sandell's sensitivity} = \frac{\text{concentration of drug} \times 0.001}{\text{Absorbance}}$$

$$= 10/0.889 \times 0.001 = 0.01124 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$$

ASSAY OF QUERCETIN IN FORMULATION (CAPSULES)

$$\% \text{ ASSAY} = \frac{\text{absorbance of sample} \times \text{concentration} \times \text{DF} \times 100}{\text{absorbance of standard} \times \text{weight of sample} \times \text{label claim}}$$

$$\text{absorbance of standard} \times \text{weight of sample} \times \text{label claim}$$

Table 7: Assay results for Quercetin in Capsule formulation

SL.NO	ABS*OF STANDARD	ABS* OF SAMPLE	%ASSAY(%w/w)
1	0.879	0.869	98.86
2	0.880	0.879	99.88
3	0.878	0.875	99.65
MEAN	0.879	0.874333	99.4633
SD	0.001	0.005033	0.535008
%RSD	0.113766	0.575664	0.537894

*Average of 3 readings

CONCLUSION:

The proposed colorimetric method was developed successfully with the 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Quercetin in methanol solvent system, showed maximum absorbance of 0.889 at 371nm. All the validation parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision and repeatability were validated according to ICH Guidelines Q2(R2). The results obtained for all validation parameters were within the acceptance criteria.

The percentage Assay for Quercetin in capsule was found to be 96.65 to 99.88%w/w which is well within acceptance criteria of 95-105%w/w and the %RSD for Assay value was 0.537894 which is well within the acceptance criteria of not more than 2%. Hence, it is concluded that developed & validated colorimetric method is simple, accurate, precise and reproducible and this method can be used for routine analysis of Quercetin in capsule formulation.

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